

ENHANCING FOURIER SERIES: POLYNOMIAL EXPANSION FOR APERIODIC FUNCTIONS ON LIMITED INTERVALS

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Abstract: *Fourier series have long been a cornerstone of mathematical analysis, particularly for periodic functions defined on intervals $[-\pi, \pi]$ or $[0, 2\pi]$, where the period 'T' plays a central role. However, when dealing with aperiodic functions defined on limited intervals like $[a, b]$, the conventional approach involves expanding them into periodic functions within the same domain. Commonly, this is achieved through half-range sine or cosine expansions, but this approach often results in periodic functions that are discontinuous or lack differentiability, causing slow convergence of the corresponding Fourier series.*

To address this issue and accelerate convergence, polynomial interpolation methods have been devised, modifying the original function using Lanczos polynomials to attain the desired smoothness. Additionally, alternative forms of Fourier series, as explored in previous works, introduce extra sine or cosine terms to the series, subsequently determining these extra terms to enhance convergence based on the desired smoothness.

In this paper, we extend the discussion beyond periodic functions by considering Fourier series expansion for functions defined on a general interval $[a, b]$. We introduce polynomial expansions that expand these functions to a larger domain, thereby achieving the desired level of smoothness and enhancing the convergence of Fourier series.

Keywords: *Fourier series, polynomial interpolation, aperiodic functions, convergence, smoothness.*

1. Introduction

Fourier series are extensively discussed for periodic functions defined on intervals $[-\pi, \pi]$, or $[0, 2\pi]$, where T is the period. For aperiodic functions defined on limited intervals, they are usually expanded to a periodic function within the same domain. Half-range sine or cosine expansions are commonly used to expand the function to a larger domain [6, 2, 4]. However, half-range sine or cosine expansions may lead to discontinuous or non-differentiable periodic functions and the corresponding Fourier series converges slowly.

Polynomial interpolation methods have been developed to accelerate the convergence of the Fourier series [3, 1]. The original function is modified by a system of Lanczos polynomials to achieve a desired smoothness. Alternative forms of Fourier series are developed in [5] to accelerate the convergence by adding extra sine or cosine terms to the Fourier series and then determine the extra terms according to the desired smoothness.

In this paper, we first consider Fourier series expansion of a function defined on a general interval $[a, b]$. Then we

introduce polynomial expansions for the function to a larger domain to achieve desired smoothness.

2. Fourier series expansion

We discuss different Fourier series expansions of defined on arbitrary interval. Without loss of generality, we assume $f(x)$ is smooth on $[a, b]$, that is, it has continuous derivatives up to any order.

2.1 Expansion to periodic function with period

A common approach is to expand $f(x)$ itself to a periodic function within the domain, that is, with period 2π . Let $x \in [0, \pi]$ and $x \in [-\pi, 0]$. Denote the extended function as $F(x)$, that is,

$$F(x) = f(x) \text{ for } 0 \leq x \leq \pi, \quad F(x + 2\pi) = F(x). \tag{1}$$

Change the variable $x \in [0, \pi]$ to $x \in [-\pi, 0]$ as

$$F(x) = -f(-x), \text{ or } F(x) = -f(\pi - x), \tag{2}$$

and denote

$$F(x) := f(x) = -f(\pi - x). \tag{3}$$

Then we have

$$F(x + 2\pi) = -f(\pi - (x + 2\pi)) = -f(\pi - x - 2\pi) = -f(\pi - x) = F(x). \tag{4}$$

Therefore, $F(x)$ is a periodic function with period 2π , and its Fourier series is given by

$$F(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [a_n \cos(nx) + b_n \sin(nx)], \tag{5}$$

where

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} F(x) \cos(nx) dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos(nx) dx - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^0 f(x) \cos(nx) dx, \tag{6}$$

$$= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos(nx) dx - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(\pi - x) \cos(n(\pi - x)) dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos(nx) dx - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \cos(n\pi - nx) dx, \tag{7}$$

and

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} F(x) \sin(nx) dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin(nx) dx - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^0 f(x) \sin(nx) dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(x) \sin(nx) dx - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(\pi - x) \sin(n(\pi - x)) dx. \tag{8}$$

Thus, the Fourier series of $F(x)$ can be written as

$$F(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [a_n \cos(nx - \pi) + b_n \sin(nx - \pi)]. \tag{9}$$

In the exponential form, (9) can be written as

$$F(x) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n e^{inx}, \quad c_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} F(x) e^{-inx} dx. \tag{10}$$

Notice that in the representations (9) and (10), there is a shift in the trigonometric and exponential terms, that is, $F(x)$ is shifted to the right by π units. However, using orthogonality conditions of functions $\sin nx$ and $\cos nx$ on interval $[0, \pi]$, we can obtain the Fourier series representation without the shift as follows. Firstly, we list the orthogonality conditions of the sine and cosine functions on interval $[0, \pi]$. Since $\int_0^{\pi} \sin nx \sin mx dx = \frac{\pi}{2} \delta_{nm}$, for any integer $n \neq 0$, we have

$$\int_0^{\pi} \sin nx \cos mx dx = \int_0^{\pi} \cos nx \sin mx dx = 0. \tag{11}$$

For any integer values of n and m , $\int_0^{2\pi} \sin nx \cos mx dx = 0$. (12)

For integers $n > 0$ and $m > 0$, $\int_0^{2\pi} \sin nx \sin mx dx = \int_0^{2\pi} \cos nx \cos mx dx = 0$, (13)

where $a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx$, $b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx$. (14)

With the orthogonal conditions, we can write the Fourier series of $f(x)$ as

$$f(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos nx + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n \sin nx, \tag{15}$$

Where a_n is the same as in (6) and

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx, \quad b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx. \tag{16}$$

The corresponding exponential form is

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} c_n e^{inx}, \quad c_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} f(x) e^{-inx} dx. \tag{17}$$

Notice that there is no shifting of x in (15) and (17).

Next, we prove the equivalence of the above representations with and without shift.

Lemma 1. *The Fourier series (9) of function $f(x)$ is equivalent to the Fourier series (15).*

Proof: It suffices to show that, for an arbitrary integer $n \geq 1$,

$$\cos nx \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{x}{2\pi} \right) + \sin nx \left(\frac{x}{2\pi} \right) = \cos nx + \sin nx, \tag{18}$$

Which can be proved using trigonometric identities as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) - \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) - \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) - \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \\
 & - \frac{1}{2} \left(\cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) - \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) .
 \end{aligned}$$

Group the similar terms together, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) - \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) - \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) \right) \\
 = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) + \sin \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \right) .
 \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2. *The complex Fourier series (10) of function () is equivalent to the complex Fourier series (17). Proof:* It suffices to show that, for an arbitrary integer ,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \cos \left(\frac{x}{2} \right) \\
 = & \dots (19)
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof is given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\dots \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\dots \right) - \left(\dots \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\dots \right) \\
 & \left(\dots \right) \left(\dots \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\dots \right) - \left(\dots \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\dots \right) \\
 = & \dots .
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the representations with shift, (9) and (10), and the ones without shift, (15) and (17), are equivalent. As can be seen from the above proofs, the value of the shift does not affect the results. Hence, we can choose any shift that is convenient for the function. If not stated otherwise, formula (15) will be used in this paper for the Fourier series of different expansions.

If () = (), the extended periodic function () is continuous everywhere. The Fourier series restricted on [,] will converge to the function () on [,], including the end points = and = . However, the function () may not be differentiable at = and = , so the convergence may be slow.

If () ≠ (), the expanded periodic function () is discontinuous at = and = . The Fourier series restricted on [,] will converge to () at the end points [6], which never converges to () and () .

Instead of applying the complicated acceleration methods proposed in [3, 1, 5] to improve the convergence rate, we will expand the function to a larger domain with polynomials to achieve the desired smoothness.

2.2 Expansion to periodical function with period 2 $= (-)$

Although half-range sine or cosine expansions are commonly used to expand a function to a larger domain, the constructed function may not be continuous. In this paper, we introduce polynomial expansion so that the periodic function is smooth of class (≥ 0) , that is, having $-$ th order continuous derivative. Let $= 2(-)$ and denote $= - = -$. We will extend the function to interval $[, +]$ then expand it to a periodic function with period $.$

We firstly expand $()$ to a periodic function of class that is continuous everywhere but may not be differentiable at ends. A simple way is to expand the function by a straight line (a polynomial of degree 1) so that the function value at $= +$ is the same as the function value at $=$. We denote this function as

$$() = \begin{cases} (), & \leq \leq \\ () + \frac{() - ()}{(-)} (-), & < \leq + \end{cases}, \quad (+ 2) = (). \tag{20}$$

Since $()$ is periodic with period 2 , the Fourier series of $()$ can be written in the form of (15) by replacing $()$ with $()$ and replacing the interval $[,]$ with $[, +]$.

Next, we expand $()$ to a periodic function of class that has continuous first order derivative. To match the derivatives at $=$ and $=$, we can choose a polynomial of degree 3 as follows

$$() = + + + , \quad \leq \leq + , \tag{21}$$

and require it to satisfy the following conditions

$$() = (), \quad (+) = (), \quad () = (), \quad (+) = (), \tag{22}$$

Where the derivatives $()$ and $()$ are one-sided derivatives. The coefficients $, (= 0,1,2,3)$ are determined by the above conditions that is equivalent to the following linear system of equations

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} () \\ () \\ '() \\ '() \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{ccc|ccc} + & & & (+) & (+) & 1 \\ & & & \vdots & \vdots & \\ \hline 3 & 2 & 1 & 0 & & \\ \hline 3 & + & & 2(+) & 1 & 0 \end{array} \right) \tag{23}$$

We denote the corresponding expansion as

$$() = \begin{cases} (), & \leq \leq \\ (), & < \leq + \end{cases}, \quad (+ 2) = (). \tag{24}$$

The Fourier series of $()$ can be written in the form of (15) by replacing $()$ with $()$ and replacing the interval $[,]$ with $[, +]$.

Remark 1: To expand the function $()$ to a periodic function of class (≥ 0) , polynomials of degree $2 + 1$ is needed.

Remark 2: For periodic function of class C^k ($k \geq 0$), the Fourier coefficients a_n and b_n satisfy (see page 130 in [6])

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n^k a_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n^k b_n = 0. \tag{25}$$

→

3. Example

We consider $f(x) = x^3$ defined on interval $[3, 4]$ and compare the three different expansions (1) , (2) , and (3) that are discussed in Section 2.

The expansion (1) has period 1 and is discontinuous at $x = 3$ and $x = 4$. Its Fourier series is given as follows

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^2} \cos(2n\pi x) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \sin(2n\pi x). \tag{26}$$

The Fourier coefficients a_n is of order n^{-2} and b_n is of order n^{-1} .

From (20), we have the expansion as

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}, & 3 \leq x \leq 4 \\ -7 + 44x, & 4 < x \leq 5 \end{cases}, \quad f(x+2) = f(x). \tag{27}$$

(2) has period 2 and is not differentiable at $x = 3$ and $x = 4$. Its Fourier series is given by

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^2} \cos(n\pi x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \sin(n\pi x). \tag{28}$$

The Fourier coefficients a_n is of order n^{-2} and b_n is of order n^{-1} .

From (24), we have expansion as

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}, & 3 \leq x \leq 4 \\ \frac{1}{2}, & 4 < x \leq 5 \end{cases}, \quad f(x+2) = f(x), \tag{29}$$

where

$$f(x) = 28x^2 - 379x + 1696x^3 - 2496x^4. \tag{30}$$

(3) has period 2 and has continuous first order derivative at all points. The second order derivative does not exist at

$x = 3$ and $x = 4$. The Fourier series of (3) is given by

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^2} \cos(n\pi x) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \sin(n\pi x). \tag{31}$$

The Fourier coefficients a_n is of order n^{-2} and b_n is of order n^{-1} .

For comparison purpose, we also obtain the half-range cosine expansion of the shifted function $f(x+3)$ defined on interval $[0,1]$ as follows

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} f(x+3), & 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ f(x-3), & -1 \leq x < 0 \end{cases}, \quad f(x+2) = f(x). \tag{32}$$

(3) is a function of class C^1 and is not differentiable at $x = 0$ and $x = 1$. The Fourier series of (3) is given by

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n^2} \cos(n\pi x). \tag{33}$$

The Fourier coefficient a_n is of order n^{-2} . We do not consider the half-range sine expansion here because the constructed periodic function will be discontinuous at $x = 0$ and $x = 1$.

From the Fourier coefficients of the corresponding expansions, we can tell that expansion with higher order polynomial to larger domain improves the convergence rate. To have a better view of the convergence, we compute the error of approximation from the partial sum of the corresponding Fourier series in (26), (28), (31), and (33).

Denote the partial sum as

The L^2 -norm of error using (1) from (2) is denoted as errorF, that is, (34)

$$\text{errorF} = \int_0^1 (f(x) - S_N(x))^2 dx \quad (35)$$

The errors using (1) , (2) and (3) are defined similarly and denoted as errorG, errorH and errorC, respectively. The errors at different values of N are presented in Table 1 and the graphs using log-log scale are shown in Figure 1.

Table 1: L^2 -norm of errors using (1) for different Fourier series

	3	5	10	20	40	80	160
errorF	8.39e-1	6.71e-1	4.86e-1	3.48e-1	2.48e-1	1.76e-1	1.24e-1
errorG	9.74e-2	5.45e-2	2.57e-2	9.15e-3	3.24e-3	1.15e-3	4.06e-4
errorH	6.46e-2	2.02e-2	2.86e-3	5.89e-4	1.12e-4	2.06e-5	3.55e-6
errorC	9.90e-2	5.52e-2	2.58e-2	9.21e-3	3.27e-3	1.16e-3	4.09e-4

Figure 1: The L^2 -norm of the errors using partial sums for different Fourier series

As can be seen from Table 1 and Figure 1, the Fourier series of (1) converges faster than that of (2) , while the Fourier series of (3) converges faster than that of (4) . (1) is nearly the same as (2) because both of them have same degree of smoothness.

Remark 3: The function (1) can be expanded to a periodic function using polynomial of higher degree following the similar procedures. For example, using polynomial of degree 5 can extend the function to class of C^5 , and the corresponding Fourier coefficients is of order $O(1/N^6)$ and is of order $O(1/N^6)$.

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